

Analysis of models applied for modelling of adaptive control for thermal energy storage system. Part 1. Models of solar collector

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Abstract: *Analysis of models applied for modelling of adaptive control for thermal energy storage system. Part 1. Models of solar collector.* This paper presents review of solar collector models focused on possibilities for simulation and implementation of these models in typical controllers, that has been applied in solar thermal system control. Models have been divided into four groups, advantages and disadvantages of each group of models were described and conclusions for practical use of models were listed.

Key words: solar collector model, solar thermal system, controller, adaptive control system

INTRODUCTION

Thermal energy storage system for energy efficient buildings (TESSe2b) is an intelligent system enabling long-term storage of heat and cold in phase change materials (PCM). The concept is based on a co-operation of solar heating system with a heat pump– for which the ground energy source will be a vertical ground heat exchanger – and heat and cold storage systems in the form of buffer tanks utilizing PCM materials. Optionally, depending on the construction of the hydraulic system, it may be required to use a plate heat exchanger operating as a separator between e.g.: solar panels and buffer tank. The various components of the TESSe2b, depending on the system location (and climatic conditions i.a.: the

duration of the heating period, the ground temperature, air temperature, insolation) should differ in size, which means that in order to optimize the system performance (energy efficiency), it is necessary to develop an intelligent (adaptive) system for operation control of the TESSe2b. One of the objectives of the intelligent control system is short-term forecast of the important parameters of the system and the time at which they will be achieved. Therefore, it is necessary to develop models of individual TESSe2b components which could enable modelling of their static and dynamic properties. Moreover, the models should be simple and implementable in the TESSe2b controller. For this reason it is essential to review the models used for modelling individual TESSe2b components.

THE MODEL REQUIREMENTS FOR AN INTELLIGENT (ADAPTIVE) CONTROL SYSTEM – THE MODELS BREAKDOWN

Each system has specific characteristics e.g.: physical, chemical, static and dynamic. In order to develop an adaptive TESSe2b control system it is necessary to know the static and dynamic characteristics of its individual components (objects

of control). One of the more convenient methods of learning about the properties of an object or a system is to develop a model mapping both, its static and dynamic characteristics. Before starting the modelling process (model creation) of a given system or object, one must select variables describing the system or object and specify the value titer range for each variable. It should be noted that the modelling process is subjective, which means that the choice of variables describing the system or object is not clear-cut and there are many ways to select variables describing the system or object. An important requirement is that the variables used to develop the models of individual components of the system have the same titer, which makes it possible to combine the models of various system components into the model of the whole system. With the model of the whole system one can simulate the operation, develop and optimize the operation control algorithm of individual system components as well as the whole system.

The model is created based on available information on a given object or system. The amount and type of information collected is determined by the type of model that should be used to model a particular object or system. If information about the static and dynamic properties of modelled object or system is available in the form of recorded time series of physical quantities, which are considered input and output values of the modelled object or system, then so-called black box method (parametric identification – IP), artificial neural networks – ANN) is used to create a model. Object model in the form of a black box makes it possible to specify the output waveform to any input (forcing) change.

When using this type of model, there is no information available about processes occurring inside the object, e.g.: if case of the thermal objects there is no information on the process of thermal exchange between the different components located inside the modelled object. There is only information available on how the object outlet temperature is affected by inlet temperature changes. Provided the information is available about physical basics of the operating of the modelled object or system, the analytical model (AM) can be applied, usually in the form of a linear differential or difference equation or in the form of state variables. Such models provide much more information about the modelled object or system than the black box models, because in addition to the analysis of how the output signal changes affect the input changes, also a thorough analysis of the operation of the modelled object is possible. Analytical models enable analysis of the processes occurring within the modelled object or system. In practice, the equivalent thermal network (ETN) based on the Beuken model is often used for the modelling of thermal processes. The Beuken model, which should be also included in a group of analytical models, is based on thermo-electric analogy – the analogy between the process of thermal exchange between two different mediums and the flow of current between these two mediums. This method involves the attempt to describe the process of thermal exchange between two mediums through the electric circuit, for which a differential equation or a system of differential equations (depending on the number of circuit elements) is formed, linking the relevant parameters of the modelled electric circuit.

The models in the form of a black box (parametric identification, artificial neural networks) and analytical models in the form of state variables allow the modelling of both, linear and non-linear objects or systems. Analytical models in the form of a differential or difference equation and equivalent thermal network allow modelling of linear and non-linear objects or systems but only around the selected operating point.

When selecting a specific model type, one should keep in mind that with certain types of models, some simplifying assumptions must be made. Simplifying assumptions arise from the capabilities of a given model type and physical properties of the modeled object. Modelled real objects or dynamic systems are usually non-stationary, distinguished by non-linear static characteristics. The modeled object or system may be a lumped- or distributed-parameter object/system. Usually, simplifying assumptions relate to linearization of static characteristics of the modeled object or system around the selected operating point and assuming stationary nature of the object at this operation point. Such simplifying assumptions are essential when using mainly analytical models based on physical basics of operating of the modeled object or system.

In order to select the optimal type of models of the individual TESSe2b components, it is necessary to analyse the technical capabilities of individual types of models for modeling the static and dynamic properties of individual TESSe2b components.

Essentially, the TESSe2b consists of the following components: solar panel (panels), compressor heat pump, ground

heat exchanger, storage buffer tanks, plate heat exchanger.

As presented in the available literature, the most commonly used for modelling the operation of solar collector are AM in the form of an differential equation or a system of differential equations derived based on the thermal balance of the homogeneous components distinguished in the design of the collector (usually, the distinguished components are: a glass cover, an absorber and a working medium). Also other types of models are applied, including both, PI/ANN and ETN.

ANALYTICAL MODELS (AM)

The task of the solar collector is to convert solar radiation into heat, which is received by the working medium constituting the medium transporting the absorbed heat to the tank. Propylene glycol is most commonly used as the working medium, which requires a heat exchanger as a separator between the medium in the tank (DHW, PCM) and glycol. Depending on the hydraulic construction of the system, the heat exchanger may be combined with a storage tank (in the form of a coil) into a single unit, or operate as a separate component, e.g. a plate heat exchanger (Reindl et al. 2008, Viessmann 2010).

Developing a proper model of the solar collector in operating conditions is difficult, because the operation of the collector is affected by many factors, e.g.: instantaneous value and variability of solar radiation, the flow of the working medium and the thermal load of the installation. Instantaneous value of solar radiation and heat removal from the installation are the interference of stochas-

tic nature. An important parameter significantly affecting the system operation, is the flow of the working medium which can be accurately regulated. Adjusting the volumetric flow of the working medium helps stabilize the system operation and optimize the delivery of accumulated heat to the tank (Farahat et al. 2009, Luminosu and Fara 2005, Obstawski 2007). Therefore, in addition to the forecast of the working medium outlet temperature, the model of the collector should be capable of simulating the effect of the volumetric flow of the working medium at a given operating point of the collector on its static and dynamic parameters.

In practice, the solar battery is designed based on knowledge of the performance characteristics of a single collector, determined experimentally in laboratory conditions using a solar radiation simulator (Kamminga 1985), or in the field based on the tests carried out in accordance with standard in effect, e.g. EN 12975-2.

The performance characteristics is included among static characteristics of the collector. It is an essential criterion in the quality assessment of collectors and allows to compare them with each other. The performance characteristics (AM) of the collector in the form of a polynomial, reflecting its static properties) is provided in the technical documentation by the manufacturer of the collector. The performance characteristics (standard characteristics) in accordance with the standard, e.g. EN 12975-2 can be determined via two methods: steady-state method and quasi-dynamic method.

The steady-state method utilizes the tests described by the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Con-

ditioning Engineers standard (ASHRE Standard 93-77), ISO 9806:1994. These are the laboratory type tests. The quasi-dynamic method (QDT) developed by Amer et al. (1999) allows to prepare AM of the collector based on measurements taken in the field. It is believed that the characteristics determined by QDT is better at mapping the static properties of the collector (Fischer et al. 2004).

Rigorous collector testing conditions imposed by standards in effect – ASHRE, ISO 9806:1994 and EN 12975-2 – are difficult to meet. This resulted in the necessity of developing other methods for creating an analytical model of the collector under transient conditions, which would in addition to static properties would also reflect the dynamic properties of the collector. These methods are classified according to various criteria (Nayak and Amer 2000). Most often they are divided due to the construction of the analytical model of the collector (AM), usually in the form of a differential equation derived based on heat exchange processes running in the collector. These are the following:

- lumped-parameter models (Perers 1993);
- distributed-parameter models (Kamminga 1985);
- models in which the coefficients are estimated at variable solar irradiance (Emery and Rogers 1984).

The disadvantage of these methods is the necessity to estimate the coefficients in the analytical model of the collector. These source methods and their modifications differ in: the process of determining the model coefficients, measurements frequency and testing methodology.

The most commonly estimated model coefficients, considered characteristic operating parameters, are the coefficients defined by the PN-EN 12975-2 standard. They are: effective thermal capacity – $(mc)_{ek}$, heat loss coefficient – U_{Lk} , collector efficiency coefficient – F' and heat removal coefficient – F_R . It is assumed that the coefficients F' and U_{Lk} define the thermal quality of the collector (Eisenmann et al. 2004).

Characteristics of collector efficiency determines its static properties showing achieved efficiency as a function of the so-called reduced temperature. For the development of the control algorithm in operating conditions it is also necessary to know the dynamic properties in both the time and frequency domains (Żółtowski 2005). The dynamic properties of a single collector in the time domain are determined based on the response to unit step function (step response) and on time constant of the collector. It can be determined experimentally in accordance with the EN 12975-2 standard or analytically.

Although the equivalent time constant is one of the most important operating parameters of the collector, it rarely is calculated and reported by the manufacturers in technical documentation. According to EN 12975-2 standard, the experiment determining the equivalent time constant it is optional. However, this does not change the fact that the dynamic properties of the collector in both the time and frequency domains are important in the operation of the solar installation system.

According to the EN12957 standard the equivalent time constant of the col-

lector is determined for one value of the working medium inlet temperature equal to the ambient temperature and for one value of the working medium flow velocity equal to 0.02 kg/m^2 (of the aperture area). The algorithm applied to determine the equivalent time constant is different than in the classic sense of the term used in automation.

Determination of the dynamic properties of the collector need not mean carrying out a separate test, specially prepared, with disconnecting the collector from the installation. They can be determined based on the known effective thermal capacity, flow and specific heat of the working medium. It is assumed that the tested collector at certain operating point is a stationary object, and therefore it becomes possible to estimate the equivalent time constant of the collector for this operating point.

One should keep in mind that in these methods the collector is not loaded with storage tank. When loaded with the tank of a certain volume, for the same operating point the effective thermal capacity of the collector may be changed, which would mean that the value of the time constant is different.

In practice, the solar set consists of several or tens of collectors connected in series or in parallel to form a so-called collector battery. Due to the testing methodology (constant working medium inlet temperature, fixed conditions), applying the above mentioned source methods and their modifications in operating conditions is limited. In addition, the dynamic properties of the solar set may change in operating conditions, depending on the load and ambient conditions.

EQUIVALENT THERMAL NETWORK (ETN) METHOD

Another method for creating a model of collector battery (connected in series or parallel) is the equivalent thermal network (ETN) method based on thermo-electric analogy. This method was first proposed by Kamminga.

The analogy is that the thermal phenomena are attributed to respective phenomena occurring in electrical circuits. The heat flow corresponds to the current flow and temperature drop corresponds to voltage decrease. Ohm's law and Kirchhoff's law are in effect in thermal as well as in electrical systems. The constructed wiring diagram creates a ETN. Solving the ETN network (calculating the distribution of the temperature and heat flux) is possible by any methods of the electrical circuits theory and using any IT tools, e.g. MATLAB.

Nodes of the circuit diagram in Figure 1 correspond to: the collector cover of average temperature – T_g , thermal capacity – C_g , the absorber of average temperature – T_p , thermal capacity – C_p , the operating medium of average temperature – T_f , thermal capacity – C_f . Heat transfer takes place through thermal resistances R , interpreted as follows: R_{ag} – total resistance to heat transfer be-

tween the cover and the environment of temperature T_a , R_{pg} – total resistance to heat transfer between the cover and the absorber, R_{pf} – resistance to heat transfer between the absorber and the working medium. The power output – $E(t)$ – of the absorbed solar radiation corresponds exclusively to the absorber. In accordance with the thermo-electric analogy, there is no description of heating of the working medium from the collector inlet temperature ($T_{f\text{inlet}}$) to outlet temperature ($T_{f\text{outlet}}$). The diagram displayed in Figure 1 was not been solved by electrical methods, and the presented ETN of the solar collector is a graphical interpretation of the system.

The method was modified by many researchers. Major modifications were introduced in the electrical diagram of the collector model, the number of homogeneous components specified in its structure and the methods of calculating each coefficient of the model. The equivalent thermal network method presented in (Chochowski 1991) seems the most complete.

The mathematical description of such a network, presented in (Chochowski 1991), is identical as in electrical circuits using Ohm's law and Kirchhoff's laws. The solution of the network is determining temperatures of the nodes and heat

FIGURE 1. Equivalent thermal network of the collector
Source: Kamminga (1985).

fluxes. The most convenient method for this is the nodal analysis.

The equivalent thermal network described in work (Chochowski 1991) was used for approximate presentation of spatial temperature distribution and heat flow propagation in the solar collector. The approximation in question results from substitution of the actual spatial thermal system characterized by distributed constants with a system of elements with concentrated constants characterized by unidirectional heat flow. The calculations apply to the average element surface temperature and volume and the average heat flows.

The equivalent thermal network is created by dividing the collector into a series of homogeneous elements of geometrically simple shapes, with the same heating and heat exchange conditions within their limits. In electric diagrams, the elements of the division correspond to the respective nodes, to which all physi-

cal properties of the element (including the thermal capacity) are assigned. The diagram node virtually corresponds to the element represented and can be conventionally assigned, e.g. to the element surface or center of its volume, or can be placed in one half of its thickness, etc. The above depends on the author's concept, but must correspond to the actual process of the phenomenon. The point of the virtual assignment of the node determines the manner of calculation of inter-nodal thermal resistances. The accuracy of representation of the collector's thermal state increases together with growth in the number of component elements, while the ETN of the solar collector consists of the equivalent thermal diagrams of such elements (Fig. 2). The diagrams are connected with one another as well as with the working medium and the environment in a manner corresponding to the heat exchange between the elements. The equivalent thermal

FIGURE 2. Graphic solution of an equivalent thermal network model
Source: Simulink.

network has n -nodes and k -branches containing thermal resistances, as well as one loss onflow point, the temperature of which is constant (ambient temperature), as opposed to the temperature of the nodes, and independent of the network thermal state. The degree of space digitization into homogeneous elements must be well thought out and must result from the need of knowledge on the thermal state of the distinguished element. Creation of a new node is not always reasonable, especially if the represented element is passive (no energy is produced), and the heat flows in branches connected thereby by conduction or convection (for example through the insulation layer). Excessive digitization hinders the thermal phenomena rather than promotes them. For instance, in our opinion, there is no need to mark out the insulation, as a homogeneous body, with a thermal network node. In general, information on the thermal state of the insulation layer or the heating process is not necessary for the analysis of the solar collector. Obviously it needs to be taken into account, but it is sufficient to use it as a heat conduction resistance.

Next to the simplifying assumptions related to space digitization, the analytical solution of the problem was also based on the condition that working parameters (such as wind speed and direction, ambient temperature, working medium flow, etc.) are constant while external constraints increase linearly. This condition can also be assumed in computations carried out in short time intervals.

The presented methods of modelling the static and dynamic properties of the

collector (collector battery) are based on analytical models in the form of linear differential equations. Using this type of models one should be aware of certain limitations e.g.: the need for linearization of the static characteristics around the selected operating point and the non-stationary nature of the collector.

Also presented in the literature are methods to estimate static and dynamic properties of the collector or collector battery on the basis of the recorded operating data. These methods use artificial neural networks (Farkas and Geczy-Vig 2003, Kalogirou 2006) or the black box approach (Baccoli et al. 2010).

ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS (ANN)

Artificial neural networks (ANN) are widely accepted as the technology offering an alternative way to solve complex problems. They are used in various applications and have proven particularly useful in the modelling and identification of non-linear systems. Literature also provides models of the solar collector, based on analogous or very similar assumptions (Kalogirou 2006). Artificial neural networks operate like a black box model and do not require detailed information about the system. A schematic diagram of a typical multi-layer architecture of the “feedforward” neural network is shown in Figure 3. Neural network usually consists of an input layer, several hidden layers and an output layer. In such simple form, each neuron is connected to other neurons of the previous layer via flexible synaptic weights.

FIGURE 3. Schematic diagram of typical multi-layered “feedforward” neural network
Source: Kalogirou (2006).

THE PARAMETRIC IDENTIFICATION METHOD (PI)

The parametric identification method (PI) was used in to model the dynamics of the solar collector. This method makes it possible to develop a model on the basis of the actual measurement data records. The set of collectors – operating in a hybrid power supply system described in Obstawski (2007) – was treated as a double-input (solar irradiance and the inlet temperature of operating medium) and single-output (the outlet temperature of working medium) object (the DISO model, standing for double input, single output) – Figure 4. In the process of

parametric identification, an appropriate type (AR, ARX, ARMAX, OE, BJ) and structure (rank) of the model can be selected with respect to best fitting the actual results.

As a result of identification the obtained model is in the form of a linear difference equation, which by means of Laplace transform can be converted into the form discrete transmittance $G(s)$, which enables the analysis of static and dynamic properties of the modelled collector (collector battery) in both, time and frequency domains.

The model of solar collectors shown in Figure 4 allows an assessment of the impact of changes in solar radiation and

FIGURE 4. The model of solar collector battery: $G_1(s)$ $G_2(s)$ – operational transmittances describing the relationship between input and output signals
Source: Obstawski (2007).

inlet temperature of the working medium on its outlet temperature. It allows to specify the nature of the ongoing transition states on the basis of response to stimulation by unit step function.

Figure 5 compares the two waveforms – actual and modeled – for the heated working medium, as performed in the study (Obstawski 2007). The comparison shows that a good convergence of actual and simulated outlet temperature of the working medium was obtained.

FIGURE 5. Comparison between the factual and the simulated temperature of the working medium
Source: Obstawski (2007).

CONCLUSIONS

In paper presented possibilities of models solar thermal collector. all types of models were divided for four groups: analytical model, neural network model, equivalent thermal network and artificial neural network. Based on analysis can be formed a few conclusions.

1. Analytical models and equivalent thermal network models in the form of an equation or system of linear dif-

ferential/difference equations based on the laws of physics.

2. The main advantages of analytical models is fact that include the capability to perform the analysis of the static and dynamic characteristics of modelled solar collector. In case of distributed-parameter analytical models it is also possible to perform the analysis of the thermal exchange process between homogeneous elements of the modelled collector, taken into account in the model.

3. The method of parametric identification, artificial neural network – also allows to create a parametric model based on recorded operating data for heavily non-linear process, which is its advantage. The IP method was successfully used to model the static and dynamic properties of both flat plate and heat pipe collector based solar set. The research was carried out in operating conditions, meaning the battery was loaded with DHW stor-

age tank. It was pointed out that the dynamic properties of both solar sets are strongly dependent on the ambient conditions.

4. The advantage of IP and ANN is the ability to determine the static and dynamic properties in the time domain for the modeled collector battery and the estimation of power output. However, due to lack of access to the internal structure of the model it is impossible to determine the characteristic parameters of the modeled solar set and the dynamic properties in the frequency domain. The main disadvantage of these methods is having an operating data of physical quantities assumed as input and output, registered in the form of time series.

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Streszczenie: *Analiza modeli stosowanych do modelowania sterowania adaptacyjnego dla systemu magazynowania energii cieplnej. Część 1. Modele kolektorów słonecznych.* W artykule przedstawio-

no przegląd modeli umożliwiających symulację właściwości statycznych i dynamicznych cieczowych kolektorów słonecznych. Analizy dokonano pod kątem możliwości implementacji modeli w najczęściej stosowanych sterownikach, co umożliwiłoby stworzenie adaptacyjnego systemu sterowania pracą słonecznej instalacji grzewczej. Modele podzielono na cztery grupy. Przeanalizowano wady i zalety każdej z grup modeli.

Słowa kluczowe: model kolektora słonecznego, system sterowania energią słoneczną instalacji grzewczej, regulator system sterowania adaptacyjnego

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